

On the Comprehensive Reform of Education

The educational system is an important component part of the superstructure of society. It plays a very important role in the consolidation and development of the socialist system and in the building of a socialist future.

Since the founding of the People's Republic of China, under the leadership of the Communist Party, the broad masses of educators and students have persevered in the great task of the socialist revolution and construction and have made brilliant achievements. But in the field of education, there still exist serious shortcomings which must be overcome in order to meet the requirements of the socialist cause.

Our educational system must adapt itself to the needs of the socialist revolution and construction and be remolded in the light of the experience gained in our practical work. In accordance with the principle of the unity of the guidance and the service functions of education, the comprehensive reform of education must be carried out with the object of serving the workers, peasants, and soldiers and promoting the all-round development of their socialist culture and education.

The following is a general outline of the comprehensive reform of education:

The aim of education

The aim of education must be to train our country's builders and successors, to strengthen the unity of the working class, the peasantry, and the intelligentsia, and to promote the all-round development of socialist culture and education.

The guiding ideology

The guiding ideology of education must be Marxism-Leninism, Mao Tse-tung's Thought, and the experience gained in the practical work of our Party and country.

The system of education

The system of education must be based on the principle of combining general education with specialized education, and combining productive labor with mental labor, so as to

train our country's builders and successors who possess both socialist consciousness and specialized knowledge and who can engage in both mental and manual labor.

The content of education

The content of education must be based on the principle of linking theory with practice and combining the study of the various sciences with the study of the revolutionary struggle and the construction of socialism.

The methods of education

The methods of education must be based on the principle of giving prominence to ideological and political education, and combining moral education with intellectual education, so as to train our country's builders and successors who have a high degree of revolutionary consciousness and are morally, intellectually, and physically developed.

The teaching staff

The teaching staff must be revolutionary in spirit, have a high degree of theoretical and cultural knowledge, be proficient in both mental and manual labor, and be able to carry out the tasks of educating and training our country's builders and successors.

The students

The students must come from among the workers, peasants, and soldiers, from poor and lower-middle-class urban and rural families, and from national minorities. The schools must give priority to educating the children of the working people.

The schools

The schools must be transformed so as to combine general education with specialized education, combine productive labor with mental labor, and combine learning with work. They must be remoulded so that they serve the workers, peasants, and soldiers and meet the requirements of socialist construction.

The national educational congress

The national educational congress must be convened to sum up our experience in educational work and to decide on the policy for the future development of education.

The comprehensive reform of education is a great revolution in the educational system. It requires the whole Party and the people of the whole country to make great efforts and to continue to struggle, in order to remould the educational system in accordance with the requirements of the socialist cause and to train our country's builders and successors who are socialist in outlook and have a high level of culture, a good command of modern science and technology, and are well-prepared politically and ideologically."

Source: "Resolution on the current education reform movement" by the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China, April 30, 1955.

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